

Participatory tools

BARCAMP

INTERNAL FUNCTIONING AND BUILDING A COMMUNITY: MANAGING THE DIVERSITY OF PARTNERS

How to deal with heterogeneous skills/experienced levels/working habits inside the consortium?

European multi-actor projects bring together very heterogeneous personalities and organisations. In a multi-actor project, they will have to collaborate. Everyone brings their own point of view and enriches the exchanges. However, difficulties can arise due to misunderstandings or (too) large gaps between habits/comfort zones.

Participatory methods allow everyone to feel understood, included, free to participate, and comfortable when participating and expressing themselves. The facilitator's posture plays an important role.

How to solve it

The first step is to gain a common understanding of each other. A language that everyone understands must be used and shared. If this is not the case initially, the partnership needs to build a common language. Partners have to avoid using overly technical/academic language that only some participants would be comfortable with.

Knowing each other is the next step. The collective work is easier if everyone knows each other and understands each other's issues, objectives and constraints. To help the process, you can alternate the venues for your meetings. If your project involves farmers and researchers, spend time in the field and in the meeting room.

Then you can exchange, share and build a way of working collectively. You can encourage experience sharing and knowledge transfer where necessary.

If not everyone has the same experience in using participatory tools, it is important to start simply at the beginning. To stimulate the exchanges, the meetings can be organised in various places. A farmer will be more comfortable and feel more able to exchange if they are in a known environment, such as on a farm. A researcher might be more comfortable in a meeting room.

Word of advice

The methods need to suit the different types of actors. It is helpful to take the time to identify these actors and their working habits, and to understand the links and power relationships that may exist. This will help you to choose the

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most suitable way to exchange. Furthermore, you can anticipate the location and timing. For example, you want to avoid milking hours if you want to bring together dairy farmers.

One example of a tool to facilitate this stage

Barcamp – We need you to choose the topic!

Description of the tool

- **What:** Share ideas and experiences, learn from each other, create a sense of community and cohesion, and work together on ideas, processes or action plans
- **How long:** 1 day
- **How many:** large and diverse groups
- **What you'll need:** circles of chairs, space, flip chart papers and coloured markers for each group

Steps:

- Set up
 - The facilitator set up the room with chairs in a circle.
 - The facilitator explains the workshop principles:
 - Whoever comes are the right people
 - Whenever it starts is the right time
 - Wherever it happens is the right place
 - Whatever happens, is the only thing that could happen
 - When it's over, it's over
 - The participants identify the topic individually, which are the ideas they want to deal with during the workshop

- Agenda
 - Any idea participants feel passionate about and want to take responsibility for can be put on a flip chart paper. The facilitator invites anyone who wants to host a group to share the topic, the location and the time needed. The information is gathered on a flip chart paper called the Agenda Wall.
- Groups talks
 - Participants are invited to join the sessions in small groups. They are free to change group at any time (the law of two feet).
- Conclusion
 - At the end, participants are invited to share their key learning points.

Testimony of the use

Robert Home, FiBL, Switzerland – case study deputy of the project Inno4wood

Inno4wood is an Interreg project gathering four organising institutions, with participation by more than 72 industry partners. The cross-border goal of the project was to facilitate access to know-how, R&D results and relevant competence centres for companies along the forest-wood value chain and thus strengthen their innovation performance.

During the European project Inno4wood, facilitators used the Barcamp tool during each general project meeting. The aim was to exchange on various topics with all the project actors. The project gathered different types of actors, including foresters (who are not overly contact-loving people), academics, and architects (who like interacting), with varying levels of knowledge of participatory methods.

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Homepage: www.liaison2020.eu

E-Mail: LIAISON2020@hnee.de

Twitter: [LIAISON2020](https://twitter.com/LIAISON2020)

This project receives funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 773418. The responsibility for the information and views set out in this document lies entirely with the authors.

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The first meeting gathered about 100 participants who formed 30 groups with four facilitators.

“The big advantage is that participants talk about the issues that are most relevant to them.” Everyone can share a topic, and participants share a common goal. “The founder of open space technology, Harrison Owen, based the method on the idea of tapping into “the most natural and essential human behaviours – self-organisation, reminding us that we know how to be together, to collaborate, and make stuff happen, with the support of simple, basic structures”. Everyone is free to discuss. This engages everyone in the project and develops relationships between project actors. The Barcamp is similar to open space technology, but participants are encouraged to spread the result of the exchanges outside the group.

“The risk, of course, is that the issues that are discussed might not be those that are most relevant to the workshop conveners.” It can be a bit scary for the facilitator the first time. It takes courage. This method requires time (one day).

Tips

- Training for less experienced actors
- A lot of support from experienced actors
- “Be brave and trust the participants!”

Another tool: word café (tool 13, [The MSP tool guide](#))

